

Providing Security Assurance & Hardening for Open Source Software/Hardware: The SecOPERA approach

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Abstract—Rapid open-source software and hardware prototyping fueled by the significant expansion of the development community, led to the deployment of highly sophisticated frameworks, solutions and products. However, as the provided open-source solutions are managed in all aspects by their designers/engineers, they lack professional evaluation of their security level. The absence of comprehensive security assessment as well as a consolidated and ubiquitous roadmap for vulnerability patching and security hardening, makes open-source solution a risk for widespread enterprise use. This paper introduces a security assurance approach which addresses open-source hardware and software shortcoming in an end-to-end manner, by providing a logical decomposition of any such module into four distinct component layers: device, network, application and cognitive. This allows highly focused security assessment, taking into consideration the specific characteristics of each layer. In addition, the paper provides an approach on how open-source solution security can be improved, through decomposition, layered vulnerability mitigation and specialized security hardening techniques. The proposed framework which is the main research and innovation focus of the SecOPERA Project intends to transform an open source solution to a protected one, as well as provide security guarantees of its overall security status.

Index Terms—Security Assessment, Security Hardening, Open Source Software, Open Source Hardware

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past few years the open-source community experienced phenomenal growth, allowing hardware and software developers to implement novel, highly sophisticated prototypes. The maturity level of these prototypes in terms of efficiency and core functionality, is often on par with that of proprietary products, leading to a sharp increase of open-source software (OSS) and open-source hardware (OSH) industrial market penetration. It was estimated that in 2022

an application included on average more than 500 open-source components [1], often implemented and maintained by numerous developer groups.

Open-source is based on a pull support model, making the users responsible for keeping track of vulnerabilities, fixes and updates for the components they use. This DevOps model often compromises security as it lacks the appropriate security guarantees introduced by processes like formal code verification and auditing, which evidently render a solution fully trustworthy. Static code analysis tools (SAST) based on whitelists for assessment are not efficient, as the collaborative nature of open-source generates immense numbers of false positives that cannot be timely addressed. Moreover, the potentially unlimited open-source project forks further complicate vulnerability tracing. In the open-source hardware domain, Intellectual Property (IP) cores offered by the open hardware community often lack security guarantees and can be prone to side channel attacks. Due to this landscape, ensuring security in any open-source solution is really difficult, leading all OEM developers and manufacturers that integrate open-source solutions to assume that third-party components need to be reassessed. To address security challenges, development teams need to have reliable and timely vulnerability information, a comprehensive inventory of the open-source dependencies their software integrates, accompanied by appropriate security guarantees. Also, a clear path is needed on how to secure the open-source solutions and harden them against unknown vulnerabilities together with a reliable mechanism that will allow the timely software patching.

This paper introduces the SecOPERA Project Consortium's approach into crafting a holistic security assurance and hardening framework, designed with complex, interconnected OSS/OSH environments in mind. SecOPERA aims to provide a turn-key solution to the open-source community of

developers, integrators and manufacturers, which will allow them to analyze, assess, secure, harden and share open-source products through a meticulous process fully compliant with the DevSecOps lifecycle. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II illustrates the fundamental concepts of the SecOPERA approach, while Section III provides an overview of the architectural blueprint. Section IV describes the evaluation strategy of the proposed solution and Section V draws conclusions and summarizes the paper.

II. MOTIVATION AND FUNDAMENTAL CONCEPTS

Acknowledging the major cybersecurity issues that stem from using open-source hardware and software in the European industry, is the first step toward finding the appropriate solution [2]. The existing landscape with its huge variety of interlinked open-source components, leads to significant dependability challenges, while sustainability is also compromised due to developer inability to allocate the necessary capacity for threat identification and timely resolution.

SecOPERA identifies dependability and sustainability of open-source solutions as the two main factors which greatly influence security. In order to achieve a certain degree of security hardening, end-to-end security guarantees need to be introduced. Since applications, products and frameworks follow multi-layer architectures, with each layer encapsulating different technical mechanics and consequently suffer from entirely different classes of attacks, any security solution must cover the full stack. Securing just the application code should be enough for defending against application-layer attacks, however, the program can be still considered non secure, since other layers on the stack may suffer from vulnerabilities. Decomposing an OSS/OSH solution into different layers is critical to the auditing functionality of SecOPERA.

A. Security Decomposition Layers

Decomposition is a custom, albeit highly systemized procedure, which accounts for any unique characteristics of a particular program. In SecOPERA any open-source solution is decomposed for identifying its basic components, which then are categorized in four (4) distinct yet interrelated layers: Device, Application, Network and Cognitive.

1) *Device Layer*: decomposition assigns all OSH components to the Device Layer, which consequently contains (i) open-source processors like RISC V architectures, and (ii) open-source hardware specification IP cores described in VHDL or Verilog which act as dedicated accelerators for an open-source processor.

2) *Application Layer*: contains the various types of application libraries including (i) open-source system libraries and (ii) operating systems for networked, memory-constrained systems with a focus on low-power wireless Internet of Things devices.

3) *Network Layer*: since many resource-savvy, interconnected devices adopt open-source network stacks to provide network capabilities to the device OS, it is necessary to aggregate all elements of the Application, Transport and network layers of the OSI model into a dedicated Layer. Moreover,

security-related network stack libraries like OpenSSL [3], are also positioned here.

4) *Cognitive Layer*: includes all Machine/Deep Learning (ML/DL) activities involved in such solutions, often deployed on edge connected devices of the Internet of Things (IoT) ecosystem [4]. This covers all open-source delivering full MLOps capabilities like OpenML project [5], as well as open-source ML/DL libraries like Tensorflow [6] or Pytorch [7]. Moreover, the Cognitive Layer also contains all open-source datasets for training/testing together with the open-source trained models.

This categorization allows the assessment of all integrated open-source solutions integrated in any connected device as a series of interrelated components, each associated with one of the above four layers, also taking into consideration the fact that these components have cross-layer data and control flow dependencies. Thus said, in order to enhance their security and certify their final status, it is necessary to introduce the concept of SecOPERA Secure Flows.

B. Defining the SecOPERA Secure Flows

A SecOPERA Secure Flow (SSF) is a series of security credentials generated through security audit/testing of open-source components, each belonging to one of the four SecOPERA Layers. An SSF is created when open-source components from different SecOPERA Layers interact using a common data and control flow and formulate an open-source solution. The SSF is possible only when the interconnected components complement each other in such a way that their interconnection doesn't introduce new vulnerabilities or threats. The SSF security credentials complement each other, given the dependencies of open-source components, and act as a comprehensive security proof of a specific open-source component flow, thus verifying that an open-source product is secure on an end-to-end manner. Finally, the SSF of an open-source component flow includes a dependability description and a history report of mitigated threats that can be used to effectively update/patch the open-source solution in the future, if one of its open-source components is no longer secure. In such a case, the SSF is broken and cannot be used to attest the security of the open-source solution. The SSF consists of dedicated nodes which capture information for each component participating in the overall security flow.

C. Cross-Layer Security Hardening Pillars

In order to verify the SSF status throughout the full OSS/OSH development lifecycle, SecOPERA introduces a series of five complementary pillars, which encompass specific techniques and mechanisms for assessing security and verifying its status per case. Every open-source component, library and technology, regardless of the stack it belongs to, is linked to both pillar and Layer and is consequently evaluated based on specific guidelines and processes.

1) *Decompose*: The decomposition pillar is the entry point to the overall SecOPERA process for evaluating open-source components, which upon receiving an open-source solution as

an input, identifies the integrated OSS/OSH building blocks it contains and then categorizes them into one of the pre-defined layers. This approach facilitates the security auditing/assessment together with the hardening process, since the components belonging to each layer demonstrate dramatically different characteristics, and thus may face dissimilar types of threats. Finally, for each of the identified components, SecOPERA identifies its dependencies and builds the corresponding dependency graphs.

Decomposing an open-source solution into multiple disjoint components has clear benefits in terms of identifying security vulnerabilities, performance issues and other potential risks. However, while going through this process, emerging challenges like (i) Complexity due to the existence of thousands of sub-components which renders the entire dependency graph analysis extremely challenging, (ii) Lack of Standardization, where different software systems may utilize various dependency management tools, file formats and naming conventions (iii) the dynamic nature of dependency graphs when components are added, removed or updated, and (iv) lack of visibility of the dependency graph, especially if components are hosted on third-party repositories and platforms, are all factors which limit the effectiveness of the dependency graph analysis and should be taken into consideration.

2) *Audit/Assess*: The audit/assess pillar in SecOPERA involves auditing and assessing open-source components for security using state-of-the-art and beyond state-of-the-art techniques and tools for each layer. First, this pillar involves techniques for static code analysis and asset risk assessment based on known vulnerabilities found in Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE) or Common Vulnerability Exposures (CVE) databases. The overall process also incorporates penetration testing methods used to discover vulnerabilities in different layers of SecOPERA, and the assessment is specialized for each layer with several different methods, such as dynamic analysis, symbolic execution, fuzzing, differential testing, and custom testing. The assessment outcome is recorded in the SecOPERA secure flow nodes and provides additional information about the discovered vulnerabilities, which can be used to enhance the security level of the OSS/OSH component.

The overall auditing and assessment process is far from being straightforward. The diversity of open-source software makes the development of a one-size-fits-all approach for security testing a challenging task, since vulnerabilities for a wide range of components, programming languages and libraries should be taken into consideration. In addition, the rapid and constant evolution of open-source software components mandates that security testing needs to be performed on a regular basis to ensure that new vulnerabilities are not introduced, especially due to the shifting security landscape where new threats and attack vectors emerge all the time. The audit/assess pillar needs to keep up with these new threats and develop innovative approaches to detect them and also take into consideration the constraints introduced by limited development resources including time, budget and personnel. The SecOPERA approach of dividing components into layers,

leads to optimal audit tools and methods utilization per layer and the application of focused security testing techniques to its components, achieving a high vulnerability detection rate with low false negatives. In addition, the outcome of the assessment process is recorded in the SecOPERA secure flow nodes that are part of the open-source solution dependency graph and contains information about the discovered vulnerabilities that can be used to harden the security level of the corresponding OSS/OSH component.

3) *Secure*: The secure pillar of the SecOPERA approach is focused on the design and development of appropriate security modules that can be mounted algorithmically or as actual software and hardware add-ons onto vulnerable open-source software or hardware components. This pillar engulfs the overall SecOPERA ecosystem security hardening approach and intends to build specified hardening components per layer. Despite the broad variety of security hardening approaches, depending on the layer of open-source software or hardware solutions that they target, their ultimate goal remains identical: to boost open-source component security especially when auditing a particular layer's component may be incomplete/inconclusive. In such cases, secure pillar modules will be applied on the layer for containing likely existing, but not yet discovered, vulnerabilities.

However, such a holistic approach introduces a series of challenges. Most devices are not designed for prioritizing security and often lack robust mechanisms for firmware updates and remote attestation that are crucial in the long-run. Additional security modules able to tackle multilayer attacks are also necessary however, such solutions based on OSH are highly specialized and introduce a significant performance overhead when integrated a-posteriori. In the presence of the constantly evolving adversarial attack landscape on ML/DL the provision of proper countermeasures is an open research problem with techniques that must be constantly updated. Aspects of privacy apart from security may also need to be addressed if private data are involved in the training or inference of an ML/DL solution and specialised privacy/security modules must be provided.

The Secure pillar is providing the main input for the Secure module pool that includes all the security hardening modules of the SecOPERA platform. Eventually, the Secure pillar's outcomes are used in the Adapt pillar to offer this pillar's security enhancements (or "hardening") service. The secure pillar research and development outcomes are meant to complement or replace some OSS/OSH components (in one or several layers), and thus provide a secure flow that can be assured by the security assurance engine as secure and trusted. The per-layer research and development done in the Secure pillar is focused on researching, designing and implementing cryptographic modules that offer next generation security (e.g., Quantum resistant), modules that can offer instruction set security extensions in open access processors and modules that can offer trusted computing capabilities and can detect memory corruption at run time. Furthermore, the Secure pillar will offer a broad range of modules/approaches that "harden"

4) *Adapt*: The scope of the adapt pillar is to provide the means to transform the integrated yet generic components of a given application into highly specialized modules that will only expose the bare minimum feature set the application requires. This process, also known as code debloating, serves two purposes (i) minimizes the size of the executables, thus reduces the functional requirements of the system and (ii) reduces the attack surface by removing unnecessary endpoints which could be exploited by an attacker. In addition, this pillar also investigates whether some third-party components could be successfully replaced by SecOPERA-compliant modules, providing a verdict regarding feature parity between the two solutions and examining necessary changes for the replacement to proceed. Again, the process contains a series of challenges since the code debloating and security enhancement processes must be carried out in the complete code base, proper specifications and functionality scenarios of the application that is tested must be defined, error-correction and compromised application functionality must be timely reported and the whole process must be developed within the resource constraints of the original project. The SecOPERA evaluation methodology takes into consideration the aforementioned limitations and will first take advantage of the capabilities of existing open-source and then will evaluate the overall process in the relevant Pilots which will be carried out based on real-world scenarios.

5) *Update/Patch*: The specific pillar incorporates a critical process which ensures the ongoing security of interconnected ecosystems, primarily designed to provide a secure and efficient mechanism for updating and patching open-source solutions. It will employ formal verification mechanisms to ensure that patches and updates are tailored specifically for the application in which they will be applied onto, while the process will be automatically triggered when any of the open-source code repositories is modified. The SecOPERA solution will encompass a dedicated unit/function that will periodically check for patches and updates, while the process will be further supported by the information available in the SSF nodes. The overall information will allow the solution to automatically assess and decide which components need to be updated and ensure that the updated flow maintains the same level of security guarantees of the original open-source flow. This will formalize and simplify the update of an open-source flow, paving the way for verifiable updates. Moreover, the updated flow will undergo re-assessment by the SecOPERA solution to make sure that end-to-end security is not compromised. Overall, the SecOPERA solution will prioritize security in the updating and patching of open-source solutions, by combining formal verification, continuous integration, and effective dependency management in order to ensure secure and efficient updates that protect against vulnerabilities and maintain the integrity of the software ecosystem.

III. ARCHITECTURAL BLUEPRINT

The SecOPERA consortium aims to design and implement a single stop Hub for improving OSS/OSH solutions in terms of security. This will be gearing architects, system designers, developers and operators with a holistic framework containing the means to analyse, assess, secure/harden and share open-source based prototypes. The proposed architecture contains several domains, components, engines, data pools, tools and services and is illustrated in Figure 1.

A. Hub Domain

The SecOPERA Hub Domain serves as the interface for software providers, integrators, administrators and other end users to interact with the entire SecOPERA framework. It consists of the *Hub Dashboard UI* which offers an intuitive and user-friendly interface, facilitating real-time insights and report visualization, and together with active user control over the various aspects of the framework. The domain also contains a series of services which support the underlying Dashboard functionality namely (a) the *Project Management* service which empowers users to create, monitor and delete projects thus streamlining project lifecycles, (b) the *Visualization* service which is responsible for notifying users of collected reports and alerts, (c) the *User Management* service, responsible for every administrative operation, (d) the *Authentication and Authorization* service which ensures robust user authentication together with cross-platform access control policy enforcement and last but not least (e) the *Management Database* that serves as a centralized repository for user profiles, roles, permissions, and project-related information within the framework. The SecOPERA Hub Domain is directly connected with the SecOPERA Hub Back-End Domain, specifically its main entity, the *Orchestrator* for exchanging information, instructions and data allowing robust system operation.

B. Hub Back-End

The SecOPERA Hub Back-End is a robust and dynamic amalgam of modules and services which underpins the platform's operations and empowers it to deliver services seamlessly, adapt to changing demand and contribute to a secure user experience. After the necessary sizing exercise, the Back-End Domain will be deployed on a cloud provider in order to ensure flexibility, reliability and scalability. The building blocks of the Back-End Domain are (a) the *Orchestrator*, a module responsible for receiving end-user requests through a dedicated API Gateway and interact with the rest of the SecOPERA modules and services for implementing business logic and oversee the generic functionality of the platform, (b) the *Secure Communication Module* which hosts the aforementioned API Gateway together with a message broker to facilitate the communication among the various components, engines and modules, (c) the *Security Assurance Process*, which provides the final confirmation that an open-source code segment is validated and secure against known and potentially unknown vulnerabilities after the audit is complete and (d)

Fig. 1. Conceptual Architecture of the SecOPERA Framework

the *Update/Patch Process*, which acts as the watchdog for tracking and evaluating changes by scanning the constantly evolving landscape of open-source software components and standards and then kickstarts the relevant update process. Several components of the SecOPERA Hub Back-End interact with the Hub Data Pool, the central information repository of SecOPERA Hub.

C. Hub Data Pool

This module acts as the central repository which integrates various components within the architecture. It is a vital element of the broader SecOPERA Hub architecture and consists of four sub-components, namely (a) the *Secure Open Source Flows Pool*, (b) the *Report Pool*, (c) the *Secure Module Pool* and (d) the *Toolbox*. The Secure Open Source Flows Pool is a repository acting as a marketplace that allows users to push/pull suitable open-source solutions. It also integrates a dedicated function for version control and updated package discovery. The Report Pool acts as the main database of service-related reports. All registered users have access to the specific database and are able to easily locate, preview and retrieve reports relevant to their role and responsibilities, whereas data privacy and security are enforced by the advanced access control and permission settings retrieved by other modules through the Orchestrator. The Secure Module Pool serves as a centralized resource for open-source secure modules, which may act as building blocks for delivering security enhancements and hardening services to existing open-source solutions with identified known or unknown vulnerabilities. The Secure Module Pool is inter-

linked with the Adaptation Engine, particularly the Security Enhancement module, in order to ensure the secure open-source module delivery which greatly impacts the overall system security. The remaining module, the *Toolbox*, contains a collection of vulnerability assessment and penetration testing tools which can be downloaded and implemented locally. The repository is constantly updated to keep pace with all emerging technologies, while remaining seamlessly integrated into the platform for easy access.

D. Enabler Technology Domain

This is the cornerstone of the overall architecture as it contains operation-critical modules, services and entities. A detailed analysis of these subsystems is presented in the following paragraphs.

1) *Decomposition and Dependability Engine*: is an autonomous component, activated by the Orchestrator in order to procure and disassemble a designated open-source solution. It adheres to contemporary best practices and methodologies, dissecting intricate open-source solutions into distinct components, carries out a comprehensive dependency analysis and generates pertinent dependency graphs which are then forwarded to the Security Audit/Testing Engine. In effect, this engine aims to streamline both the security audit and testing process, allowing for a more focused security analysis of each component, and, subsequently, the security enhancing phase, by targeting patches exclusively toward the identified vulnerable components, bolstering their defenses effectively.

2) *Security Audit/Testing Engine*: receives the decomposition outcome from the relevant module through the Sec-

OPERA message Translator/Adapter and further progresses with the security assessment. Depending on the Layers the open-source components have been linked with, the Engine invokes the corresponding component. The (a) the *OSH Security Assessment* unit, (b) the *Application Security Assessment* unit, (c) the *Cross-Layer Penetration Testing* unit, (d) the *Cognitive Security Assessment* unit are in charge of assessing components linked with Device, Application, Network and Cognitive Layer respectively, while (e) the *Knowledge Base Vulnerability Assessment* unit retrieves CWE (cataloging software weaknesses and vulnerabilities) / CVEs (cataloging and tracking software and firmware vulnerabilities) from third-party vulnerability knowledge databases.

When viewed from a functional perspective, the *OSH Security Assessment* unit intends to evaluate a solution's resilience against implementation attacks (mostly side channel attacks) on a provided OSH IP core that performs a specialized security operation. Through a series of tests the unit can provide accurate assessment on vulnerabilities which could potentially compromise a cryptography/security primitive peripheral or a crypto-accelerator/processor. Moreover, SecOPERA integrated components able to identify SCA vulnerabilities (both generic and profiling), detect hardware trojans through abnormal leakage discovery of microarchitectural attacks [9] via trace input collection. The unit will rely on a side channel leakage trace collection engine with high flexibility as presented in [10] and [11].

The *Application Security Assessment* unit is triggered by requests originating from the Orchestrator and kickstarts a series of configuration and static code analysis tests, after reaching out to external CWE/CVE knowledge bases for the necessary updates. Built on top of a series of common tools like FRAMA-C [12] and PyCG [13], leverages their detection abilities and ensures comprehensive security evaluations which are then forwarded to the Hub Dashboard after being converted into user-friendly reports.

Functionality-wise, the *Cross-Layer Penetration Testing* unit aims to assess Network Layer security by conducting penetration tests which simulate real-world cyberattacks together with structure assessments, vulnerability scanning, post-exploitation activities and thus uncover existing weak points. Besides the proactive security weakness identification, penetration testing provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of existing security measures and helps making informed decisions about security investments.

In terms of functionality, the *Cognitive Security Assessment* unit is equipped with an array of tools and mechanisms designed to assess the resilience of open-source ML models implemented using popular libraries, evaluate them in the context of contemporary security and privacy threats thus identify potential vulnerabilities and bugs that could be exploited by sophisticated adversaries.

3) *Adaptation Engine*: consists of two main components, the *Code Debloating* unit, tasked with removing parts of the software that are not utilized by the final product and consequently reduce the attack surface and the *Security Enhance-*

ment unit which intends to ensure that the resulting debloated code will be properly fed to the Security Audit/Testing Engine and thus help users select the optimal modules from the SecOPERA Hub pools.

4) *SecOPERA Message Adapter*: Is the basic communication component of the overall platform, introduced due to its microservice-based architecture. These adapters will be present to every domain to ensure service interaction but also minimize the underlying system complexity, promote flexibility and improve fault tolerance and responsiveness. Based on the requirements of the platform, indicative capabilities of the SecOPERA message adapters may include API Endpoints, Data transformation and protocol conversion. In general, message adapters are particularly valuable for implementing event-driven architectures, where services react to events or changes in the system, making them an essential part of modern microservices-based applications.

IV. EVALUATION STRATEGY

The functionality of the proposed architecture will be validated via two dedicated Pilots which contain carefully selected scenarios and use cases directly leveraging a wide spectrum of the innovations introduced by the SecOPERA solution.

A. Pilot 1 - Secure supply chain in automotive industry

The first Pilot addresses certain supply chain issues found in the automotive industry and involves two partners: PINNO and VoXel who have a long relationship as OEM and Tier 1 supplier. Throughout their collaboration, VoXel together with PINNO design, manufacture, and deploy hardware/software solutions mainly for prototyping and testing purposes. In a typical scenario, PINNO and VoXel hold joint development sprints for designing the hardware and bringing up the software of the developed platforms. It is of paramount importance that the development operations between PINNO and VoXel are highly secured and compliant to protect the privacy of their customers while ensuring availability and nominal operations of their joined products. To that end, both parties aim to leverage the innovations of SecOPERA in order to establish high-quality DevSecOps based on open-source tools and methodologies – which in turn also focus on open-source software too. In detail, both PINNO and VoXel envision to utilise the following SecOPERA components: (i) methodologies for achieving ISO-compliant DevSecOps, (ii) tools and techniques for verifying the developed software and hardware, and (iii) tools and methodologies for secure software updates, threat analysis and monitoring during operations.

B. Pilot 2 - Critical IoT Infrastructure for Water Management

The second pilot aims to increase the security of a series of IoT devices implemented by GREEN, a manufacturer with limited cybersecurity experience which provides solutions for managing water infrastructure including sewer network, drinking water and irrigation network. Similar yet more simplistic solutions have been presented in [14] and [15]. However,

unlike the aforementioned examples, GREEN manages a real-world smart watering solution deployment for the city of Marseille, designed to exhibit substantial reductions in water usage for irrigation purposes. As member of the SecOPERA consortium, GREEN will use the newly introduced technologies applications and methodologies of the SecOPERA framework to increase its cybersecurity culture, increase the security level of its next IoT device generation, and comply with security standards. This radical approach will allow GREEN to conduct a real-world evaluation of the proposed benefits and assess the behavior of their newly designed products, namely (i) a native smartphone application embedding Bluetooth connectivity based on an open-source flutter framework and (ii) a new IoT hardware and firmware embedding NB-IOT and Bluetooth connectivity, in the field. As cybersecurity is becoming a “must have” for large scale deployments in any smart city solution, the SecOPERA solution will introduce significant competitive advantages.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The SecOPERA Project aims to provide a comprehensive framework for promoting the security of any OSS/OSH module. Its scope is to equip open-source developers, researchers and manufacturers with a toolbox for analyzing, assess and enhance their respective solutions and construct more solid, highly secure elements for larger projects to build onto. DevSecOps lifecycle support together with appropriate, verifiable security guarantees denoted as SecOPERA open-source flows and SecOPERA secure flows respectively, are fundamental aspects of the proposed approach.

OSS/OSH solutions using the SecOPERA framework are decomposed into four different groups and are analyzed so as to fully map their codebases and respective dependencies. They are then thoroughly assessed/tested against known vulnerabilities with respect to the different category each open-source component belongs to, in a generic manner for all types of structural components. Identified flows are secured/hardened through the provided modules of SecOPERA Hub, while the integrated updating/patching mechanism of the framework ensures that these flows remain secure even a new vulnerability is identified for one of their open-source starting points. Last but not least, debloating mechanisms for limiting the attack surface area are also integrated, thus delivering all features but with a minimized software bundle.

SecOPERA provides an open-source repository of modules and already hardened solutions, a holistic framework for augmenting security but most importantly, it hands out to the open-source community a European-scale playground that will boost collaboration and kickstart a pan-European, security-focused OSS/OSH collaborative ecosystem.

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